

SHORT NOTES

Kinetics of the Oxidation of Malic Acid by Ce(IV) Sulphate

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In the previous communications¹⁻², the kinetic studies of the oxidation of mandelic, lactic, glycollic, tartaric, malonic, and pyruvic acid by cerium (IV) salts have been reported. In the present communication the author has studied the kinetics of oxidation of malic acid by Ce(IV) sulphate under a variety of conditions.

The materials employed were of the highest purity available. Malic acid (Light & Co.) was purified by recrystallisation and the solution was standardised against NaOH. The details of the other reagents and kinetic measurements by iodometric method have been described in the previous communications¹⁻².

Induced Reduction of Mercuric Chloride.—Following Waters and Levesley³, mercuric chloride was also found to be reduced during the oxidation of malic acid by Ce(IV) salt, indicating formation of a reducing intermediate, *i.e.*, free radical.

Order of Reaction.—The order of the reaction was found to be the same as described in a previous communication². From the slopes of the $\log a/(a-x)$ vs. t plot, the velocity constants were calculated, including 7-9 experimental points.

Dependence of Velocity Constant of H₂SO₄ concentration.—The oxidation process was studied in solutions containing different amounts of acid. The reaction was retarded by H₂SO₄. The results are recorded in Table I. The plot of $\log K$ against $\log [H_2SO_4]$ is linear and the product $K[H_2SO_4]$ provides fairly constant values (Fig. 1).

TABLE I

Temp. = 30° $[H_2SO_4] = 0.112M$. $[Ce^{IV} \text{ sulphate}] = 0.0240M$.

[Malic acid] (M)	..	0.01225	0.0082	0.0048	0.0024
$K \times 10^3$ (sec ⁻¹)	..	9.211	6.525	3.480	1.726
$K/[Malic]$	..	0.752	0.794	0.725	0.717

Effect of Salts.—Different salts, such as NaClO₄, MgSO₄, Na₂SO₄, have been used. The results are recorded in Table II. No effect on the rate was observed with NaClO₄. All the other three retarded the rate of reaction. In other sets, reaction velocities were measured at different concentrations of the salts like Na₂SO₄ and MgSO₄. The reaction

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1. Sengupta *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, 40, 823; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1963, 38, 25.

2. Sengupta, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1964, 2, 267; this *Journal*, 1964, 41, 427, 423; D. Phil. thesis, Calcutta University, 1963.

velocity diminished as sulphate-ion concentration was increased, though not according to any mathematical regularity.

TABLE II

[Malic acid] = 0.01225M. (Ce^{IV} sulphate) = 0.0240 M. [H₂SO₄] = 0.120M.
Temp. = 25°.

[Salt] × 10	..	0	2.5M-NaClO ₄	2.5M-MgSO ₄	2.5M-Na ₂ SO ₄	2.5M-KHSO ₄
K × 10 ³ (sec ⁻¹)	..	4.907	4.907	2.301	1.535	0.767

Dependence of Rate of THF—water Binary Mixture.—The reaction was studied in various THF—water binary mixtures. The velocity constant increase was found to exhibit a linear relation with % solvent (Fig. 2).

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

Influence of Temperature.—The velocity constants were calculated at different temperatures. All the experiments were performed at identical [H⁺]. The results are recorded in Fig. 3. From the slopes of the log K vs. 1/T plot, the activation energy was calculated. The values of activation energy are represented in Table III.

TABLE III

[Malic acid].	[Ce ^{IV} sulphate].	[H ₂ SO ₄].	E (kcal.).
0.00930M	0.0187M	0.123M	11.7 ± 0.5
0.00879	0.0136	0.278	20.7 ± 0.7
"	"	0.541	25.3 ± 0.9
"	"	0.833	27.6 ± 0.8
"	"	0.880	29.9 ± 1.3

On oxidation of malic acid with large excess of Ce⁴⁺ ion, CO₂ was evolved and formic acid remained in solution; a total of about 8 equivalents of Ce⁴⁺ ions was eventually

consumed per mole of malic acid and one mole of malic acid produced two equivalents of formic acid. Consequently,

would represent the stoichiometry of the equation. The oxidation product, formic acid, was confirmed by the chromotropic acid reaction.

The stages through which the reaction proceeds can be explained on the basis of free radical mechanism, similar to the scheme suggested by Levesley and Waters³. Malic acid reacts with Ce^{4+} ion to give rise to an activated complex. The immediate change in colour from orange $\rightarrow$ red clearly shows the occurrence of the complex formation. The complex decomposes slowly to provide a free radical, Ce^{3+} ion, and H^+ ion. This free radical takes up further Ce^{4+} ion and by the fast step provides an aldehyde, which forms a precipitate with 2,4-DNP.

Similarly, an aldehyde is also the initial product of oxidation of malic acid when it is oxidised by quinivalent vanadium⁴. The subsequent steps are considered to be very fast.

Again, it has been observed that the rate constant decreases with the increase of $[H_2SO_4]$. This is probably due to the fact that Ce^{4+} ion forms stronger complexes with sulphuric acid. This may also be explained in the light of the oxidation potential data of $Ce(IV)-Ce(III)$ system which depends on acidity and particularly on the kinds of anion present⁵. As the concentration of H_2SO_4 is raised, the oxidation potential of $Ce(IV)-Ce(III)$ system gradually diminishes; consequently, the reaction will be retarded requiring a greater energy in the medium.

In rapid radical reactions⁶, the activation energy is found to be small and lie far below the energy required to dissociate chemical bonds involved (60—100 kcal.). The low activation energy values at different sulphuric acid concentrations also support the above picture of free-radical mechanism.

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3. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 217.

4. Jones *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1961, 630.

5. Smith and Duke, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1943, 15, 120.

6. Walling, "Free Radicals in Solution", p. 59, 1957, John Wiley & Sons.